

Free Ligand Exponent of Monoprotic Ligands

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Manuscript received 15 September 1975, accepted 23 July 1976.

A new method for calculation of free ligand exponent of monoprotic ligands, that is, the ligands which can take up only one proton is proposed. This does not require the acid dissociation constants of the ligands and the pH of the medium.

The successive stability constants for complexes in solution are very often determined by Bjerrum, Calvin pH titration technique¹ as modified by Irving and Rossotti². To calculate the constants prior measurement of the values of $\bar{n}_A$ (proton-ligand formation function), $\bar{n}$ (metal-ligand formation function) and pL (free ligand exponent) are necessary. The general expression for $\bar{n}_A$ is

$$\bar{n}_A = \frac{\sum_{j=0}^{j-1} \alpha_j \beta_j^H [H]^j}{\sum_{j=0}^{j-1} \beta_j^H [H]^j} \quad (1)$$

where these terms have their usual significance³ and the charges are omitted. The expression (1) implies that the hydrogen ion concentration is the only independent variable for $\bar{n}_A$. The working formulae for $\bar{n}_A$ and $\bar{n}$ are³,

$$\bar{n}_A = Y + \frac{(V' - V'') (N + E^0)}{(V^0 + V') T_{L^0}} \quad (2)$$

$$\bar{n} = \frac{(V''' - V'') (N + E^0)}{(V^0 + V') \bar{n}_A, T_{M^0}} \quad (3)$$

The terms have their usual significance. The expression (3) shows that $\bar{n}$ can be calculated directly from the experimental curve, and that no knowledge of hydrogen ion concentration is necessary. But to obtain the pL values, the proton-ligand stability constant of the ligand and the hydrogen ion concentration (or the B value in case of water-dioxan medium) are required. The working formula in aqueous solution is³

$$pL = \log_{10} \left\{ \frac{\sum_{j=0}^{j-1} C \beta_j^H [H]^j}{(T_{L^0} - \bar{n} T_{M^0})} \times \frac{V^0 + V'''}{V^0} \right\} \quad (4)$$

and in water-dioxane medium is,

$$pL = \log_{10} \left\{ \frac{\sum_{j=0}^{j-1} P \beta_j^H \left[\frac{1}{\text{antilog} B} \right]^j}{(T_{L^0} - \bar{n} T_{M^0})} \times \frac{V^0 + V'''}{V^0} \right\} \quad (5)$$

where $C \beta_j^H$ and $P \beta_j^H$ are stoichiometric and practical proton-ligand stability constants respectively.

But the following arguments reveal that for the monoprotic ligands, that is, the ligands like acetate ion, ammonia etc which can take up only one proton (or the ligands whose conjugate acids are mono basic), pL can be directly calculated from the titration curves and no knowledge of the pH or $C \beta_1^H$ are required.

For a monoprotic ligand the equation (1) simplifies to

$$\bar{n}_A = \frac{C \beta_1^H [H]}{1 + C \beta_1^H [H]} \quad (6)$$

$$\therefore 1 - \bar{n}_A = \frac{1}{1 + C \beta_1^H [H]} \quad (7)$$

when the equation (7) is combined with equation (4) simplified for a monoprotic ligand. We get,

$$pL = \log_{10} \left\{ \frac{1}{(T_{L^0} - \bar{n} T_{M^0})(1 - \bar{n}_A)} \times \frac{V''' + V^0}{V^0} \right\} \quad (8)$$

or in general

$$[L] = (T_{L^0} - \bar{n} T_{M^0})(1 - \bar{n}_A) \quad (9)$$

The same expressions may be derived from equation (5) by making appropriate substitution for $P \beta_1^H$. Since these equations do not involve $[H]$ (or B) or the proton-ligand stability constants $C \beta_1^H$ (or $P \beta_1^H$) it follows that pL can be calculated without any knowledge of these values in either aqueous or mixed aqueous solvents, using only values of $\bar{n}_A$ and $\bar{n}$ derived from the experimental curves using equations (2) and (3). This would simplify calculations of metal-ligand stability constants and points to the fact that the measurements can certainly be extended to other mixed aqueous solvents.

An important corollary to equation (8) is the case when $\bar{n}_A = 1$. In certain cases [Fig. 1] mineral acid curves and the ligand (HL) curves do not separate at low pH regions (i.e. $V'' = V'$ in equation (2) but the metal-ligand curves separate. This occur with several ligands viz. phenols^{3,4}, amides⁵, oximes⁶ etc. The non-separation of the mineral acid and ligand curves along a range of pH indicates that the $\bar{n}_A \approx 1$ and that HL is undissociated in the pH range. This means that $[L] \approx 0$ (equation 9).

FIG 1
pH titration curve

Such reactions should be regarded as taking the following course,

And so the equilibrium constant

$$K = \frac{[ML][H]}{[M][HL]}$$

should be considered.

In such cases the stability constants can be defined,

$$\beta_1 = \frac{[ML][H]}{[M][HL]} ; \beta_2 = \frac{[ML_2][H]^2}{[M][HL]^2} ; \beta_n = \frac{[ML_n][H]^n}{[M][HL]^n} \quad (10)$$

$$\therefore \bar{n} = \frac{\beta_1[M][HL] + 2\beta_2[M][HL]^2 + \dots + n\beta_n[M][HL]^n}{[M] + \beta_1[M][HL] + \beta_2[M][HL]^2 + \dots + \beta_n[M][HL]^n} \quad (11)$$

$$= \frac{\sum_{n=0}^{n=n} n\beta_n \frac{[HL]^n}{[H]^n}}{\sum_{n=0}^{n=n} \beta_n \frac{[HL]^n}{[H]^n}} \quad (12)$$

$$\therefore \sum_{n=0}^{n=n} (\bar{n} - n) \beta_n \frac{[HL]^n}{[H]^n} = 0 \quad (13)$$

Now the free ligand concentration $[HL] = \text{Total HL concentration } (T_{HL}) - \text{concentration of HL which has reacted with metal}$

$$\therefore [HL] = T_{HL} - \bar{n} T_M \quad (14)$$

The calculation of β_n in such cases, however, involves the determination of $[H]$.

References

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